

Response to JPL Open Sourced Science (OSS) for NASA Earth System Observatory (ESO) Mission Science Data Processing Study Request for Information (RFI)

Name: ESA EO Open Science

Description: This document is a response to the JPL OSS for NASA ESO Mission Science Data Processing Study Request for Information (RFI). The proposal includes contributions from ESA EOP-S and ESA EOP-G. Point of contact of the organization: Anca Angheloa, Claudia Vitolo, Clement Albinet, Klaus Scipal

Relevant past experience:

ESA's core Earth observation research and development programme FutureEO promotes **Open Science** solutions as a driver of scientific innovation. A unifying principle of all data exploitation activities in FutureEO-1 Segment 2 is the enhancement and acceleration through cutting-edge technologies such as AI powered OpenEO platforms, Data Cubes, Cloud Computing and Big Data analysis, **Open Science** approaches and Citizen science. The programme builds on outcomes from EOEP-5 and FutureEO-1 Segment 1, obtained in the frame of several EOP-S and EOP-G activities whose implementation will adhere to Open Science principles. Here we present some of the most prominent ones, addressing elements related to Data Processing System Architectures and Open Science. Lessons learnt from these activities will feed the design of the ESA EOP-S Open Science Framework.

Background information:

In 2020, NASA, ESA, and JAXA combined forces using open science principles to accelerate scientific analysis and communication of the impacts of COVID-19 via a set of indicators derived from tri-agency EO Data. The EO Dashboard is based on the Open Source software project EODASH (<https://github.com/eurodatacube/eodash>). Initially developed to support research on the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic, the EO Dashboard provides satellite-informed indicators of societal, environmental, and economic impacts. The for EODASH relies on the Euro Data Cube (<https://eurodatacube.com>) for the backend services, including: data access and analysis, storage and distribution, exploitation and collaboration. The EO Dashboard activity enables a series of exploratory R&D activities and community engagement, in an Open and Reproducible Science approach. This activity laid the foundation for a new programmatic element.

As part of the EO for Society element, ESA adheres to Open source science practices to enlarge the commercial and scientific user base for European Earth Observation and increase participation. Notably, ESA Virtual labs are platform services for scientists to share data resources in an enhanced research environment. Additionally, free Open Source toolboxes are provided for the scientific exploitation of EO missions, enabling access to software, documentation and tutorials, collaborative development and dialogue within the community.

To help scientists in the above ground biomass community and to support the science for the upcoming BIOMASS satellite missions, ESA is building a cloud-computing platform called Multi-Mission Algorithm and Analysis Platform (MAAP, <https://scimaap.net>). The MAAP is jointly developed and implemented with NASA and will include data (satellite, airborne, in situ data and products), high performing computing capabilities and tools and algorithms. To ensure that users are able to collaborate across the platform and to access needed resources, the MAAP requires all data, algorithms, and software to conform to open access and open-source policies. As an example of collaborative and open-source best practices, the BIOMASS data processing algorithms are developed on MAAP under the umbrella of the Open Source scientific Software BioPAL (<https://www.biopal.org>, <https://github.com/BioPAL>). In addition to aiding researchers, the MAAP will focus on sharing data, science algorithms and compute resources to foster and accelerate scientific research.

Response to Data Processing System Architecture:

ESA has experience with complex data processing system architectures, supporting efficient processing of large and heterogeneous data sources. Digital Twin technologies, for instance, are currently being designed to be user-centric and provide an array of microservices to enable flexible orchestrations of scientific workflows. The technologies build upon robust current operational systems such as Copernicus, Euro Data Cube, OpenEO Platform, MAAP. Below we provide details of some of the most recent and relevant systems.

Euro Data Cube is the main tool supporting the EO Dashboard project. It is a one-stop-shop for browsing, analysis and processing of EO data, from source to the final product. It provides access to complete global EO archives from open missions (e.g., Sentinel, Landsat, MODIS, etc.), commercial satellites (PlanetScope, Pleiades, SPOT, WorldView, etc.) and Level 3 products (Copernicus Land Monitoring Services, C3S, etc.). EDC is built to complement EO data archives and ICT resource platforms like the

Copernicus DIAS or AWS and has an Open architecture relying on adopted standards to maximise interoperability. Among the added value services of the EDC are: 1) Sentinel Hub - Cloud API to most important EO datasets ; 2) Batch Processing - heavy-duty processing tasks for large-scale analysis and machine learning; 3) xcube - perfectly customizable analysis and processing based on xarray technology; 4) geoDB for geospatial vector data and Sentinel Hub for raster data; 5) EOxHub Workspace – managed compute and storage environment to run Jupyter Notebooks and host own applications; 6) Marketplace for free or revenue-generating options to share data, applications and algorithms GitHub repositories for public contributions of code and algorithms.

OpenEO platform (<https://openeo.cloud/>) is an ESA initiative developing an open and operational platform service based on the openEO API (the latter was developed under H2020 funding to address interoperability shortcomings among existing EO platforms). A key aspect guiding the development of openEO platform is the abstraction of underlying complexity, which is addressed at various stages of a typical EO workflow e.g. through the use of virtual data cubes and predefined process building blocks. Users interface with the platform through front end libraries available in Python, R and JavaScript. The initial platform architecture is based on a federated deployment in three European public cloud environments: TerraScope, EODC and CreoDIAS. In

addition, a data federation allows serving collections and optimised layer from Euro Data Cube. The federation is extendible and more cloud backends will be added in the future. Hosted Jupyter lab notebooks are the primary development environment in openEO platform while desktop based development environments (e.g. PyCharm) are also supported. The openEO platform Web-Editor additionally provides a graphical workflow builder, where graphical workflows (called openEO process graphs) can automatically be translated into different programming languages. The Web-Editor also provides batch job process monitoring functionality to the user.

ESA has experience with complex data space architectures, such a Copernicus, DestinE and DTE&U. In such complex projects, users are instrumental to the system architecture design. Digital Twin activities, for instance, adopt an open design approach. User requirements are captured before the project starts through several User Engagement Workshops. User needs are prioritized and a number of use cases are selected, which are used to design the very first draft of the system architecture and platform functionalities. During the project, frequent interactions with different communities and stakeholders (e.g., Member States) take place. User feedback at various stages contribute to the objectives of the following development cycle. Direct contributions are also envisaged to be incorporated into the system (e.g., open software, models, etc).

The Biomass MAAP provides cloud based computing resources as well as access to Level-1 and higher Level data of the BIOMASS mission and complementing missions. The architecture is tailored to the needs of an Explorer mission, i.e. rapid processor evolution and testing and reprocessing activities.

Response to **Open Science**:

ESA adheres to Open Science in many aspects of the technological development of Earth Observation exploitation solutions and methods. These span from the open sharing of data (e.g., Copernicus), information (RACE Dashboard) as well as modelling and analytics tools (future Digital Twin activities, Euro Data Cube, MAAP, SNAP, Virtual Labs). All the development activities rely on the use of version control systems, while data is curated and citable. Wherever possible licenses are permissive, repositories are public and reviews are put in place to generate trust in the community. Below we provide details of some of the most recent and relevant activities.

Euro Data Cube supported public competition activities such as the [EO Dashboard hackathon](#) or the [RACE Challenges](#) allowing interested parties to make use of the data without investing time in basic data access and pre-processing tasks. Participants to these competitions received access to all the EDC tools, integrated into EOxHub Workspace, which allowed them to prototype the process from the data to the extracted information. The EOxHub Workspace with the managed EDC JupyterLab provided means for scripting and execution of Jupyter Notebooks. Through the provision of tutorial notebooks, participants could reproduce the scientific workflows and generate on their own the same indicators displayed on the dashboard, and furthermore to easily craft computational narratives on top of the indicator data. This allowed to speed up the development process, shortening the time between concept, prototyping, integration and deployment. Through this mechanism, the community contributed [interesting ideas and prototypes](#), but also some operational solutions, which were integrated into EODASH.

In the past decade ESA has been developing Open Innovation tools to enable collaborative Earth System Science research, starting with the game-changing Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP), which marked a corner stone in the exploitation of Open EO data. With almost 1 million downloads, today SNAP is evolving into a full open tool, developed with and for the community, scalable and adapted to new cloud computing environments.

Looking at the future of open science tools, ESA has launched a new suite of available and upcoming Virtual Laboratories: Atmosphere Virtual Lab, Cryosphere Virtual Lab, Agriculture Virtual Lab, Ocean Virtual Lab, Deep Earth System Data Lab (DeepESDL). These Open-Source virtual research environments aim to make EO data, information and tools readily accessible to scientists, promoting the sharing of data, knowledge, tools and results and enabling collaborative research. As an example of how Open Science principles are addressed in the Virtual Labs, the DeepESDL has an agile-first design, including elements to facilitate open and collaborative algorithm development and scientific research: straightforward discovery mechanisms for EO-based products, datasets and workflows using open standards, enhanced capacity for distributed teams to retrieve and jointly process these data with their own algorithms as well as by reusing workflows and algorithms from collaborative groups, tools to evaluate and curate outputs of the processing, access to advanced visualisation tools and sharing the results, etc.

To support the open sharing of data, information, analytics, and knowledge transfer within the scientific community and the wider public and to accelerate scientific research the BIOMASS mission will provide an open data platform (MAAP, <https://scimaap.net>) providing open access to Level-1 and higher-level data. In addition, the operational processor is made available in an open repository (<https://github.com/BioPAL>) and developed in the frame of an Open-Source software project. Validation data is made available openly through <https://forest-observation-system.net/> to enable a transparent and reproducible assessment of algorithms. With respect to an Open Science based mission operation following elements should be considered:

- Open data access: Level-1 and higher-level data ideally in an Analysis Ready data format including auxiliary data required for processing.
- Computing resources: scalable cloud based computing resources with a direct access to the data archives.
- Open access to processors: Processors need to be designed and structured such that elements can be easily integrated in workflows.
- Support to processor evolution: processors need to follow open-source software guidelines. It is important to note that this does not only require an Open License but a number of supporting elements (a governance model, code of conduct, contribution guidelines, documentation guidelines, project website, communication channels, packaging and distribution strategy, CI/CD strategy, testing environment, etc.). Ideally the Open-Source Software project should be supported by an Open-Source specialist.
- Open access to validation data and standardised validation protocols ideally agreed by CEOS to allow a transparent and reproducible assessment of EO products.
- Access to a DOI certifying system to provide DOIs to documents and data.
- Open training courses.

Response to Downstream Interoperability

Over the past year, ESA, in collaboration with NASA, Natural Resources Canada and a set of expert industrial providers, have been analysing possible solutions in the [OGC](#) (Open Geospatial Consortium) framework, where standards and best practices for the benefit of the geospatial community are defined. A dedicated [EO Exploitation Platform Domain Working Group](#) has been created to drive the change on such a high-interest topic. ESA contributed to various OGC [testbeds and pilots](#) (starting from testbed-13 in 2018), as part of the [EO Exploitation Platform Common Architecture \(EOEPCA\)](#) programmatic activities. Such in-depth practical experience paved the way to define best practices in setting up cloud environments and in coding applications that can be dynamically deployed on various cloud infrastructures (*bring the user/application to the data* paradigm).

Scrutinised and approved by the EO Exploitation Platform Domain Working Group, the OGC Technical Committee and the OGC Planning Committee, the [Best Practice for Earth Observation Application Package \[OGC 20-089r1\]](#) has been [released](#). It includes guidelines – based on the use of the [Docker](#) industrial standard and a set of suitable OGC APIs – to develop easily deployable applications for cloud environments aligned to provided indications.

ESA is taking a number of actions to streamline use of the defined guidelines.

An open source *platform-out-of-the-box* has been made available through the EOEPCA: it can easily be deployed on any cloud providing a [Kubernetes](#) environment, also known as the “operating system of the clouds”. EOEPCA *platform-out-of-the-box* allows platform operators to deploy an OGC-compliant platform to host and share applications. It comprises the following components:

The open source platform can be easily deployed using [helm chart](#) packages and all necessary support by the open source team is ensured by ESA. An [introductory presentation](#) gives an overview of the components that can be deployed. The Application Deployment and Execution Service (ADES) is the minimum mandatory environment to make the infrastructure interoperable, allowing deployment and execution of applications. In 2022 ESA intends to perform the roll-out of this interoperability layer by two independent platform operators – TerraDue and Space Application Services – who will operate their Algorithm Hosting services on multiple clouds of the [Network of Resources](#). By using these services to host an application, it’s guaranteed that it can be easily executed on different cloud environments.

Links to publicly available publications and relevant resources that support the response

1. EODASH <https://github.com/eurodatacube/eodash>
2. Euro Data Cube <https://eurodatacube.com>
3. MAAP <https://scimaap.net>
4. BioPAL <https://www.biopal.org>
5. BioPAL GitHub <https://github.com/BioPAL>
6. OpenEO platform <https://openeo.cloud/>
7. EO Dashboard Hackathon [EO Dashboard hackathon](#)
8. Rapid Action on Covid-19 and EO challenges [RACE Challenges](#)
9. RACE Challenges winner <https://eo4society.esa.int/2021/07/08/race-challenges-2021-first-winner/>
10. Forest Observation System <https://forest-observation-system.net/>
11. Open Geospatial Consortium [OGC](#)
12. EO Exploitation Platform Domain Working Group <https://www.ogc.org/projects/groups/eoexplatform>
13. OGC Testbeds and Pilots <https://www.ogc.org/projects/initiatives/completed>
14. EO Exploitation Platform Common Architecture (EOEPCA) <https://eo4society.esa.int/common-architecture/>
15. Best Practice for Earth Observation Application Package [OGC 20-089r1] <https://docs.ogc.org/bp/20-089r1.html>
16. OGC Best Practice for EO Application Packages <https://www.ogc.org/pressroom/pressreleases/4656>
17. EOEPCA Presentation https://eoepca.org/docs/13/3_Phi-week_2021-10-15_RC.pdf
18. ESA Network of Resources <https://eo4society.esa.int/network-of-resources/>